

MULTISPIN.AI

AI Co-Processor Research Project

D6.2

Dissemination and Communication Activities Plan

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Project Details

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Consortium:

Id	Participant Name	Short name	Country
1	BAR ILAN UNIVERSITY	BIU	ISRAEL
2	INESC MICROSISTEMAS E NANOTECNOLOGIAS - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES PARA OS MICROSISTEMAS E AS NANOTECNOLOGIAS	INESC MN	PORTUGAL
3	UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN	UCLouvain	BELGIUM
4	SPINEEDGE LTD	SPINEEDGE	ISRAEL
5	INTERACTIVE FULLY ELECTRICAL VEHICLES SRL	IFEVS	ITALY
6	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	BELGIUM

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Executive Summary

The communication plan for the MultiSpin.AI project aims to ensure clear and consistent dissemination of information both internally and externally. Its main objective is to raise awareness and maximise the visibility of the project and its results while protecting its intellectual property. Internally, regular meetings and email updates will promote transparency and collaboration between partners. Externally, a clear communication strategy will be deployed through various channels such as press releases, social media, and the project website. The publication of scientific articles in top-level journals will also be prioritised to increase the project's impact. The timeline runs from February 2024 to January 2027, with specific milestones for the launch of online platforms, press releases, publication of scientific papers, and engagement with industrial partners and the scientific community.

1 Objectives

The objectives of the Dissemination and Communication Activities Plan of the project are to:

- Raise awareness and maximize the visibility of the MultiSpin.AI project and its results.
- Publish more than 4 scientific papers in high-impact journals.
- Protect the intellectual property (IP) of the project results.
- Establish and maintain communication and informative (social) media channels.
- Develop an exploitation roadmap for the project results that lead to innovation in the field.

2 Communication Strategy

2.1 Internal Communication

- Hold regular meetings with project partners, in connection to the general project meetings and in addition, as needed, to discuss progress, milestones, and dissemination activities in collaboration with the project coordinator.
- Utilize internal communication channels such as email and messaging for quick updates and information sharing.
- Ensure transparency and collaboration among all partners to facilitate effective communication through internal communication channels.

2.2 External Communication

- Development of a professional Research Project Brand and Brand book.
- Develop a clear and consistent messaging strategy to communicate project objectives, achievements, and impacts to external stakeholders:
 - Utilize various communication channels such as press releases, newsletters, social media, and project website to disseminate project updates and news.
 - Tailor communication materials to suit the interests and preferences of different stakeholder groups, including the scientific community, industry partners, policymakers, and the public.

2.3 Scientific Papers

- The primary objective is to enhance the visibility and impact of scientific papers by strategically targeting high-impact journals such as Nature, Applied Physics Letters, Electronics, and Physical Review Applied. The quality, relevance, and rigor of the research findings will be ensured through close collaboration with project partners, thereby increasing the likelihood of acceptance in these prestigious publications. Additionally, we will prioritize open-access publication to maximize the accessibility and reach of our research outputs, enabling broader dissemination and engagement within the scientific community and beyond.

2.4 Intellectual Property

- Implement appropriate measures such as patents, copyrights, and non-disclosure agreements to safeguard project results and innovations.

3 Dissemination strategy

3.1 Project website

- Establish and maintain a dedicated project website to serve as a central hub for project information, updates, and publications.
- Include sections on research findings, project objectives, consortium partners, contact information for inquiries, news and events.

3.2 Social Media Presence

- Maintain active profiles on popular social media platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and ResearchGate to share project updates and engage with stakeholders.
- Regularly post about project milestones, publications, and upcoming events to keep followers informed and engaged.

3.3 Press Releases and Media Outreach

- Draft press releases highlighting key project achievements and research findings for distribution to relevant media outlets.
- Build relationships with journalists and industry publications to secure coverage of project developments and outcomes.
- Build relationships with network organisations and their communication channels / activities.

3.4 Engagement

- Engage with industry partners and stakeholders to showcase project results and explore potential collaboration opportunities.
- Participate in events, conferences, and workshops to present project findings and network with industry professionals.
- Link with networks and organisations in the field of AI research and Spintronics specifically.

4 Timeline

4.1 February 2024 - April 2024:

- Project Website and Social Media Setup:
 - Launch the MultiSpin.AI project website with essential information about the project objectives, consortium partners, and contact details.
 - Create social media profiles on platforms such as LinkedIn, Twitter, and ResearchGate to start building an online presence.

4.2 May 2024 - July 2024:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.

D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Activities Plan

- Develop a comprehensive external communication strategy outlining key messages, target audiences, and communication channels.

4.3 August 2024 - October 2024:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.
- Press Releases and Media Outreach:
 - Draft press releases highlighting project milestones, research findings, and upcoming events for distribution to relevant media outlets.
 - Reach out to journalists and industry publications to secure coverage of project developments.
- Social Media Engagement:
 - Start posting regular updates and news about the project on social media platforms to engage with stakeholders and build a following.

4.4 November 2024 - January 2025:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.
- Scientific Papers:
 - Support the dissemination of scientific papers to high-impact journals such as Nature, Applied Physics Letters, Electronics, and Physical Review Applied.
- Industry Engagement and Collaboration:
 - Initiate discussions with industry partners to explore potential collaborations and opportunities for technology transfer and commercialization.

4.5 February 2025 - April 2025:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.
- Publication and Dissemination:
 - Publish scientific papers accepted by high-impact journals, prioritizing open-access options to maximize accessibility and impact.
 - Disseminate published papers through various channels, including the project website, social media, and press releases.

4.6 May 2025 - July 2025:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.
- Conference Presentations and Workshops:
 - Present project results and findings at relevant conferences, workshops, and industry events to engage with the scientific community and industry stakeholders.
 - Host a workshop on neuromorphic computing to share the project vision and results with the scientific community.
- Stakeholder Updates:
 - Provide project partners and the European Commission with updates on project progress and achievements via regular mailing campaigns.

4.7 August 2025 - October 2025:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.
- Academia and Industry Collaboration:
 - Collaborate with European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) and industry partners to demonstrate the Proof of Concept (PoC) and engage in further collaboration activities.

4.8 November 2025 - January 2026:

- Continuously monitor and update the website and social networks, provide partners and collaborators with updates via mailing campaign.
- Networking and International Events:
 - Participate in major summits, tradeshow, and international events to showcase project results and network with stakeholders.
 - Explore linkages with other relevant projects and network organizations to expand collaboration opportunities.
- Workshop:
 - Host a workshop on neuromorphic computing to share the project vision and results with the scientific community.

4.9 February 2026 - January 2027:

- Ongoing Communication and Exploitation:
 - Maintain regular communication and engagement with stakeholders through mailing campaigns, social media updates, event participation and organization, and collaborations.
 - Continuously monitor and update the roadmap to adapt to changing market conditions and opportunities.

5 Conclusion

The MultiSpin.AI Communication and Dissemination Plan outlines a comprehensive strategy for disseminating project findings, engaging with stakeholders, and maximizing the impact of MultiSpin.AI's innovative technology. The activities outlined in this plan will make the project's results accessible to all in accordance with the practice of open science.

The plan focuses on developing and disseminating scientific publications, presenting at international conferences, and organizing workshops to foster knowledge exchange. Active participation in scientific events will raise awareness of the scientific results and provide networking opportunities, while targeted communication strategies will effectively engage key stakeholders. By enhancing collaboration, visibility, and understanding, this plan aims to contribute significantly to advancements in neuromorphic computing and artificial intelligence.

By implementing this plan, MultiSpin.AI aims to enhance collaboration, raise awareness, and contribute to advancements in neuromorphic computing and artificial intelligence.